

International Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Development

Available online on
http://www.rpublication.com/ijeted/ijeted_index.htm
ISSN 2249-6149

ARTICLE INFO

©2026 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJETED-
69EBF225813BF

Published: 2026-05-12

DOI:
<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20137387>

Page No: 15/1-15/14

FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS OF MINI-HYDROPOWER GENERATION AT ARINTA WATER FALLS, IPOLE-ILORO, EKITI STATE, NIGERIA.

¹*Afuye E.K, ²Rominiyi O.L and ³Lasisi I.O

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, The Federal
Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

²Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, Afe Babalola
University, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, The Federal Polytechnic, Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: ✉ ezekielafuye418@gmail.com, ☎ +2348087360842

ABSTRACT:

Energy plays the most vital role in the economic growth, progress, and development, as well as poverty eradication and security of any nation. Uninterrupted power supply is a vital issue for many countries today. Future economic growth crucially depends on the long-term availability of energy from sources that are affordable, accessible, and environmentally friendly. Hydroelectric Power is a form of renewable energy source that has being in existence for quite a long time in advanced countries. Other renewable resources include geothermal, wave power, tidal power, wind power, and solar power. The aim of this paper is to study Arinta Water-falls as an initiative for harnessing electric power from mini-hydro production. It is established that the obtainable head and flow rate available during the selected months of the raining season at Arinta water falls should be sustainable for mini-hydro power plant. The effect on the ecosystem is very less, the ecotourism will attract visitors and the living standard of the people in the area will improve after commissioning of a mini-hydroelectric power station. Hence, the problem of in- adequate electric power production would be improved by using sustainable technology.

KEYWORDS: Mini-hydroelectric, Energy, flow rate, Arinta Water fall, Ekiti, Nigeria

Cite This Paper: Afuye E.K, Rominiyi O.L and Lasisi I.O (2026). "FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS OF MINI-HYDROPOWER GENERATION AT ARINTA WATER FALLS, IPOLE-ILORO, EKITI STATE, NIGERIA.". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EMERGING TRENDS IN ENGINEERING AND DEVELOPMENT (IJETED)*, vol. 16, Issue 3, 2026, pp. 15/1-15/14. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20137387>

INTRODUCTION

Energy is one of the most fundamental elements in the world. Energy is used for operating machine, light homes and cities, power vehicles, trains, aero-planes, musical equipment, television and other home appliances. Energy is a necessity for human survival in the universe. Nigeria is seriously facing energy demand predicament and the bad-state of power has been the major bane of it's under development, (Aliyu, 2019). Hydroelectric power has played an important part in the development of this Nation's electric power industry. Both small and large hydroelectric power developments were instrumental in the early expansion of the electric power industry, (Anund, 2020). Hydroelectric power comes from water at work, water in motion, winter and spring runoff from mountain streams and clear lakes. Water, when it is falling by the force of gravity, can be used to turn turbines and generators that produce electricity. Hydroelectric power is important to our Nation. Growing populations and modern technologies require vast amounts of electricity for creating, building, and expanding. In the 1920's, hydroelectric plants supplied as much as 40 percent of the electric energy produced (Bala, 2014) Although the amount of energy produced by this means has steadily increased, the amount produced by other types of power plants has increased at a faster rate which means that hydroelectric power now have a lesser percentage of the world electrical energy (Hollaway, 2013). Hydropower is an essential contributor in the national power grid because of its ability to respond quickly to rapidly varying loads or system disturbances, which base load plants with steam systems powered by combustion or nuclear processes cannot accommodate 58 power plants throughout the Western United States produce an average of 42 billion kWh (kilowatt-hours) per year, enough to meet the residential needs of more than 14 million people. This is the electrical energy equivalent of about 72 million barrels of oil. Hydroelectric power plants are the most efficient means of producing electric energy (Fasele and Hosking, 2013) The efficiency of today's hydroelectric plant is about 90 percent. Hydroelectric plants do not create air pollution, the fuel (falling water) is not consumed, projects have long lives relative to other forms of energy generation, and hydroelectric generators respond quickly to changing system conditions, (Emmanuel and Robert, 2011). These favorable characteristics continue to make hydroelectric projects attractive sources of electric power. It can be seen as a form of solar energy, as the sun powers the hydrologic cycle which gives the earth its water. In the hydrologic cycle, atmospheric water reaches the earth's surface as precipitation. Some of this water evaporates, but much of it either percolates into the soil or becomes surface runoff. Water from rain and melting snow eventually reaches ponds, lakes, reservoirs, or oceans where evaporation is constantly occurring. The energy consumption pattern in Nigeria shows that natural gas

accounts for 5.22 percent, hydro-electricity accounts for 3.05 percent, fuel wood accounts for 50.45 percent, while petroleum products accounts for 41.23 percent. Hydropower generation is responsible for substantial part of electricity generation mix in the country. Small hydropower estimated capacity in the country, as of 2006, is put to be at about 734 MW and is available in all part of the country (Ramchandra and Bouca, 2010 and (Thomas and Williamson, 2020) This is likely to increase as more investigation is carried out. If the capacity is fully developed, it can generate nearly 20 percent of present national combined generation from both fossil and thermal source of electricity. China has set the pace and standard for both the developed and developing countries to emulate as it has the largest install capacity of small hydropower globally (UNIDO, 2013) There is no universally accepted definition of the term

—small hydro which depending on local definitions can range in size from a few kilowatts to 50 megawatts a more of rated power output. International, —small hydro power plant capacities typically range in size from 1 MW to 5 MW, the 100 kW to 1 MW range sometimes referred to as —mini hydro and projects under 100 kW referred to as —micro hydro. Installed capacity, however, is not always a good indicator of the size of hydro project. Table 1 dictates the scale and capacity range of hydro power plants. (Afuye and Olubakin, 2018)

Table 1: Classifications of Various Hydro Schemes

Scale of hydro scheme	Capacity Range (MW)
Large	100
Medium	>50 – 100
Intermediate	10-50
Small	1-10
Mini	0.5-1.0
Micro	< 0.5

At the end of 2002, 42,221 SHP installations have been built with a total installed capacity of more than 28,489MW. These installations produce annually a total of 98.7 Billion kWh of SHP.

Electricity plays a very important role in the socio-economic and technological development of every nation. The electricity demand in Nigeria far outstrips the supply and the supply is epileptic in nature. The country is faced with acute electricity problems, which is hindering its development notwithstanding the availability of vast natural resources in the country. (Afuye and Oluwaleye, 2016) It is widely accepted that there is a strong correlation between socio-economic development and the availability of electricity. The low power generation in Nigeria had hindered her economic growth and industrialization.

It has affected areas such as Agriculture, Food production and processing, Water Supply etc. Currently, only 40 % of Nigeria's population is connected to the energy grid whilst power supply difficulties are experienced around 60% of the time (Aliyu *et al.*, 2019) At best, average daily power supply is estimated at four hours (PWC, 2016), although several days can go by without any power at all. Power supply difficulties cripple the agricultural, industrial, and mining sectors and impede Nigeria's ongoing economic development (Kaseke and Hosking, 2013), the energy supply crisis is complex, stems from a variety of issues, and has been ongoing for decades. The development of electricity in Nigeria started in 1896, Lagos with the installation of a thermal power station of 30KW capacity (Oyedepo, 2012) On the other hand, hydro power development surfaced near Calaba in present day Cross River state as far back as 1912, but was later abandoned. Other projects sprang upon Central Nigeria around Jos Plateau. The first such development was at Kwall falls, near Jos, in 1923, when a 4.0 MW pelton turbine power station was built. Small Hydro-projects became more popular River Basin Authorities were created in the 1970s. Projects involving Small Hydroplants included Challawa Gorge Dam, Bakolori Dam, Jibiya Dam, Goronyo Dam, Tiga Dam etc. Surprisingly, of these, only Oyan Dam, Bakolori Dam and Ikere Gorge Dam were actually built. When power demand escalated in 1960, emphasis was on the development of large Hydro Power projects to meet the demand Nationwide, (Afuye and Oluwaleye, 2014) Arinta formerly known as Erinta waterfall is located in Ipole Iloro Ekiti, it is 6 km away from Ikogosi warm spring tourist centre, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The town is located in Ekiti State of Nigeria which is situated in the heart of the tropics of the country. It is located between longitudes 40 451 to 50 451 east of the Greenwich Meridian and latitudes 70 45, 81 501 north of the equator. The state comprises of sixteen (16) Local Government Areas (LGAs) with its state headquarters at Ado-Ekiti. The State is mainly an upland zone that rises over 250 m above the sea level. With temperature ranges between 21 °C to 28 °C and a high humidity, two distinct seasons are witnessed in the state, which are raining season, between April and October and dry season between November and March. (Ajani *et al.*, 2015) It could be reached only through a secondary road from Ikogosi. The road leading to the fall passes through the Ikogosi Tourist Center.

Tourists felt the chilly effect of this fall about 10 meters away. It has three pronounced escarpments. This resort center is naturally endowed with thick and evergreen forest. The Arinta waterfalls are a wonder spectacle to behold, cascading down rocky hills from a great height to form a flowing pool of spring water amidst natural forest vegetation. They are located in Ipole-Iloro Ekiti and are a popular tourist site that draws local and foreign tourists to the State. —Arinta ever wet ever flowing, the obsession of Ipole

people, ever plunging ever splashing! The steep slopes of the overawing ridge, panoramas of a beautiful valley trapped between two ridges meet the eyes. The landscape features a sprawling expanse of lush vegetation set with a patchwork of rust-brown ‘_tabs’ at a distance, and a sky-line bedecked with gently undulating ridge tops on the other side. The noon-day sun energized the verdural flavour of the valley below, casting it in a harmonious romance of bright and dark shades of leaf green. Figure 1 shows the geographical location of Arinta Water Falls at Ipole Iloro Ekiti, Figure 2 is the Map of Ekiti State showing the Local government where Ipole Iloro Ekiti can be found and Figure 3 is the Geographical Location of Ipole Iloro Ekiti.

Figure 1: Geological Map of Ipole showing Arinta Waterfall

Figure 2: Map of Ekiti State

Figure 3: Geographical Location of Ipole Iloro Ekiti

Plates 1(a) shows Arinta water fall and (b) shows first level of Arinta water fall. The river has about seven steps and three major falls as shown in Plates 1 (c) and (d).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Plate 1: Views of Arinta waterfall

The water does not dry off, even during the typical dry season. The tarred road descends down the other side of the ridge to meet the sleepy enclave of Ipole-Iloro. A small stream meets the road at the village entrance. It is called Oluwa stream, and being highly-revered by the people, it is said that the water can cure any kind of diseases. The enclave holds a total human population of about eight hundred people. Aayo spring can be seen winding its way across the village, dividing the village into two parts. The first part towards the south holds the area where the ancestors of Ipole-Iloro people first dwelt before expansion took the boundaries of the village beyond the river to the other side. This cultural landmark constitutes a major landmark in the enclave and it's highly treasured by the people.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

When rain water falls over the earth's surface, it possesses potential energy relative to sea or ocean towards which it flows. As the water falls through a certain vertical height, its potential energy is converted into Kinetic energy and this kinetic energy is converted to the mechanical energy by allowing the water to flow through the hydraulic turbine runner. This mechanical energy is utilized to run an electric generator which is coupled to the turbine shaft (Rajput, 2000).

Let M (kg) of water be stored at an altitude in meters above the turbine position. If the acceleration due to free fall is g (m/s^2)

The potential energy E_p of the water at that altitude is given by;

$$E = MgH \quad (1)$$

Since the density, d , of a substance is the ratio of the mass to volume, V .

$$d = \frac{m \text{ (kg)}}{v \text{ (m}^3\text{)}} \quad (2)$$

$$m = dv \quad (3)$$

\therefore Substituting equation (3) into (1),

$$E = dvgh$$

Since the density of water is 1000 kg/m^3

$$\therefore E_p = 1000 vgH$$

But, Power is energy per unit time,

$$p = \frac{1000vgH}{t}$$

$$p = 1000 \frac{v}{t} gH, \text{ where;}$$

$\frac{v}{t}$ is the volume flow rate of the water, q ($\frac{m^3}{s}$)

$$p = 1000qgH \quad \text{in Watts} \quad (\text{Rajput, 2000}) \quad (4)$$

If the turbine efficiency η is taken into consideration

$$p = 1000\eta qgH \quad \text{in Watts}$$

Where, $g = 9.81$

$$p = 9810\eta QH$$

Therefore,
$$p = \rho gQH \quad (5)$$

Meanwhile, for standard and experimental influence, the formula, $p = \rho gQH$ was used

Where, Q is the rate of water flow, m^3/sec . H is the height of fall or head, m , η is the efficiency of conversion of potential energy into mechanical energy.

The generation of electrical energy from falling water is only a small process in the mighty power cycle known as Hydrological cycle or rain evaporation cycle. Data on rainfall in the proposed mini- hydro station area were collected for a period of one year of dry and wet seasons from the year 2021 to 2022. The elevation of Arinta waterfalls was obtained from literature to be within the range of 455 m to 495 m but the minimum is used to generate the power in Table 2.

. The flow rate of water fall was measured with a bucket and using a stopwatch for timing the period to fill the bucket. The time taken to fill 9 litres bucket ranges from 3.5 to 7.2 seconds.

$$\text{Power output} = 1000 \times \text{Head} \times \text{Flow} \times \text{acceleration due to gravity} \quad (6)$$

Using 9 litres bucket and a stop watch, the flow rate was obtained using equation (7)

$$\text{Flow rate} = \frac{9 \text{ litres m}}{\text{Time taken to fill up the bucket (seconds)}} \quad (7)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Flow rate can be calculated for each selected month in the dry and rainy seasons that is November to March and April to October. Power output for each month was calculated using the minimum head and the flow rate obtained for each month in Table 2.

Table 2: Monthly highest low rate and highest power generated at an instant

Months	Flow Rate (m ³ /s)	Power output (Kw)
November	1.25	568.75
December	1.26	573.3
January	1.26	573.3
February	1.38	627.9
March	1.8	819
April	2.5	1137.5
May	2.5	1137.5
June	2.7	1228.5
July	2.72	1237.6
August	2.63	1196.65
September	2.72	1237.6
October	2.81	1169.35

From the obtained data, it was observed that the maximum and minimum flow rates were 2.81 m³/s and 1.38 m³/s respectively for the experimented year. The power generation capacity with respect to the flow of the water is exposed in the Table 2. The water flow in a day is near steady. An extensive study has been carried out on the feasibility of hydroelectric power generation in Arinta Waterfall. It is expected that the surveyed site be used as test for a designed model in the future. The results obtained in this study showed that mini hydropower plant (SHP) can be sited in the selected site; Arinta Waterfall. Figure 4 is the comparison of the flow rates (m³/s) and months from January to December.

Figure 4: Graph of Flow Rates against Months

The flow rate is at its maximum in the month of October and has minimum value in the month of November. Figure 5 is the graphical relation between power output and the various Months under study.

Figure 5: Graph of Power Output against Month

The maximum and minimum power outputs are 568.75 Kw and 1169.35 Kw respectively. The values fall within the range of power obtainable from a mini hydropower scheme. This simply means that the site has the tendency of producing mini hydropower. The results also show that the higher the volume or quantity of water, the higher the power produced and vice versa. For the purpose of verification, a cross flow turbine or waterwheel can be manufactured to test the hypothesis.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained revealed that Arinta waterfall is a prospective site for a mini hydro power generation which could add to the success of energy needs necessary to meet electricity demands of the Nation. A cross flow turbine or a water wheel will be the best for power production from the results. The flow rate of the waterfall was gotten to be fairly constant throughout the year with little alterations as a result of rainfall during raining season and lack of it during dry season. The maximum theoretical power was found to be 568.75 Kw and the minimum theoretical power was found to be 1169.35 Kw meaning that the generator is flexible enough to cover range 500 – 1000 Kw.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are hereby put forward for consideration to harnessing and developing mini-hydro power for the Arinta waterfall.

- i. It would be suggested that the awareness be made to the necessary authorities and institutions in the Energy sector to see it as a priority in maximizing the water bodies around the nation to generate electricity.
- ii. A designer of a chosen turbine to produce the power needed must be very careful when planning the scheme not include unnecessary components to avoid the malfunctioning of the scheme
- iii. The Government of Ekiti State should work with private sector that will make use of hydropower potentials in the state to solve power problems.
- iv. More study on energy uses and transformation should be encouraged in Institutions of higher learning.
- v. Government at various levels should pay attention to renewable energy resources by allocating more resources to it in the budget.
- vi. Governments should provide fiscal incentives for prospective investors in the energy sector such as corporate tax waivers.
- vii. Government should foster financial partnership between developed and developing Countries through the international funding agencies such as IMF, UNCDP, UNIDO, World Bank, etc.
- viii. It is recommended that further study be done on this site to maximize its usage for power generation.

REFERENCES

- Afuye, E. K. (2016). Design and Construction of a Cross flow Turbine system for a Mini-Hydropower Plant as a Boost for Renewable Energy system. Master's degree dissertation, Ekiti state university, Ado-Ekiti, pp. 11-15 & 75. Unpublished
- Afuye, E.K and Oluwaleye, I.O (2014). Hydropower Potential for power Generation in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Journal of Engineering and Earth Sciences, Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti. Volume 8 No1, pp. 78-87
ISSN: 1897-8680
- Afuye, E.K and Olubakinde, E. (2018). Development of A Cross Flow Turbine System for a Mini Hydropower plant as a boost to strengthening Industrialization in Nigerian Engineering Conference of the Nigerian Society of Engineers, Ado-Ekiti Branch.
- Ajani, F, Olufemi, O. O. and Fadeayo, A. A. (2015). Department of Wildlife and Ecotourism Management, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria. Wikipedia. Retrived on, 25th January, 2021.
- Aliyu, U. E (1999). Prospects for Small Hydropower Development for Rural Application in Nigeria. Journal for Renewable Energy, pp74-86
- Aliyu, A., Ramli, A., and Saleh, M. (2013). Nigeria electricity crisis: Power generation capacity expansion and environmental ramifications. Wikipedia, 61(8), 354-367. Retrieved on, 5th January, 2021.
- Aliyu, U. E. (2000). Assessment of Small Hydropower Potential in Nigeria. An invited paper presented at a public lecture organized by Nigerian Society of Engineers, Bauchi Branch, October 26, 2000. pp 2,3 and 4.
- Aliyu, U. E. (2003). Small Hydropower Design: Matching of supply and demand. Unpublished B.Sc Thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi.
- Anund, K. (2020). Future Energy, (3rd Edition). Retrieved on 20th December, 2025
- Bala, E. J. (2014). 5-day Training Course on conducting feasibility studies on small Hydro plants by renewable academy (RENAC). Germany, and Retrieved on, 5th January, 2025

- Daily Trust, Online (2012). An Inside look at Kainji. Retrieved on January 21, 2024
- Emmanuel, I. I. and Robert, B. J. (2011). Small hydropower development in Nigeria: issues, challenges and prospects. Retrieved on 17th November, 2022
- ESHA—European Small Hydropower Association, (2004). Guide on How to Develop a Small hydropower Plant, Chapter 1, Introduction. ESHA, Brussels, Belgium, 2004,
http://www.esha.be/fileadmin/esha_files/documents/publications/GUIDES/GUIDE_SHP/GUIDE_SHP_EN.pdf,
retrieved on, 2nd February, 2026
- ESI Africa (2021). Plans afoot to modernize generation unit at Nigerian hydro Plant. Rondenbosch' South Africa: ESI Africal, retrieved on 3rd February, 2021.
- Hollaway, L. C. (2013). Advanced fibre Reinforced polymer (FRP): Composite structure applications. High-Performance Construction Materials, pp207-263 (2008),
https://doi.org/10.1142/9789812797360_0005, retrieved on 16th Jan, 2021.
- International Energy Agency, (2019). Renewable electricity generated by source (Non-combustible) in 2014 (IEA, 2016) and 2017 (IEA, 2019)ll, retrieved on 16th January, 2025.
- International Energy Agency, (2016). Global-scale yearly growth rate (2010-2015) in renewable energy. Retrieved on 14th October, 2024.
- International Energy Agency (2018): —Global-scale yearly growth rate (2010-2015) in renewable energy. Retrieved on 14th October, 2025.
- Inacio-Ferreira, J. H., Camacho, J. R & Malagoli, J. A. (2016). A Contribution to the Study of the Estimate Hydroelectric Potential for Small Hydropower Plant. Retrieved from DOI:10.1109/TLA.2016.7587623 on 25th Nov, 2025
- Kasele, N. and Hosking, S. (2013). Sub-saharan African Electricity Supply Inadequacy: Implications. East Africa Social Science Research Review 29(2), 113-132, Organization for Social Science Research in Eastern and Southern Africa. Retrieved February 25, 2014, from Project MUSE Database.

Inacio-Ferreira, J. H., & Camacho J. R. (2016). Micro Hydro Energy Resources in Bangladesh, a review. Australian journal of Basic and Applied sciences 2(4):1209-1222, 2008. TSSN 1991-8178 0, 2008, ENSTnei publication

Jerome, C. U. (2006). Detailed project report writing – Guidelines. Retrieved on, 16th October 2022

Shinn, L. (2018). Renewable Energy: the clean fact. Retrieved on, 6th December, 2022 <https://www.nrdc.org/stores/renewable-energy-clean-facts>.

Oyedepo, S. O. (2012). Energy and sustainable development in Nigeria: the way forward. Retrieved on 5th August, 2022. Energy Sustain Soc 2, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-0567-2-15>.

PWC, (2016). PwC's Annual Power and Utilities Roundtable: The challenges with transforming the Nigerian power landscape. Doi:10.1016/j.energy.2013.09.011

Rajput, R. K. (2000). A Text Book of Fluid Mechanics and Hydraulic Machines. ISO9001, Schand Publishing ISBN 81-219-1666-6. Pp. 1070 & 1071.

Ramchandra, P and Boucar, D (2010). Green Energy and Technology. Springer, London Dordrecht Heidelberg, New York

Sunday O. O., (2012). Energy, Sustainability and Society, 2:15, retrieved on, 4th September, 2025.

Taylor, S., Upadhyay, D. and Laguna, M. (2006). Renewable Energy world. Retrieved on, 4th March, 2022. pp. 126-131.

Thomas, R. and Williamson, S. H. (2020). What was the U.S GDP Then?: Measuring Worth. Retrieve on, September 22, 2025.

UNIDO (2013). Summary of small hydro potential in Nigeria. www.unido.rc.org/Nigeria. Retrieved on 13th February, 2025.

UNIDO (2005). Renewable Energy for Rural Industrialization and Development in Nigeria. www.unido.rc.org/Nigeria. Retrieved on 15th November 2025.

UNIDO (2006). Electricity Generation through small hydropower for Sustainable Development in Africa. www.unido.rc.org/Nigeria. Retrieved 6th January, 2025